

856 Appendix A: Additional LTE model figures

Fig. A.1: Reduced χ^2 values for each LTE model. A value near 1 indicates a good fit. The species are listed by column, and the clumps by row. The clumps are indicated by black stars and the N44 dusty condensations MM1 and MM2 are labelled '1' and '2', respectively.

Fig. A.2: The model spectrum for each of the three species in the central pixel of N44. The first three columns show the LTE model and the last column shows the RADEX model. The data are in solid black, the overall LTE model is in solid pink. The LTE components are indicated by dashed or dotted coloured lines: the dashed orange and purple are the warm components of each species, the dotted yellow and blue are the cold components in CH_3OH , and the dotted teal is the broad outflow component. The dot-dashed blue line is the total RADEX model. The upper energy level of each transition line is noted on the plot, with its frequency at the source v_{LSR} shown as the vertical grey line.

Fig. A.3: Same as Fig. A.2 for the outflow component of N44. This pixel is three pixels, or $6''$, west of the central pixel in N44, and is where the outflow component is seen to be the most prominent.

Fig. A.4: Same as Fig. A.2 for the central pixel of N48.

Fig. A.5: Same as Fig. A.2 for the central pixel of N38.

Fig. A.6: Same as Fig. A.2 for the central pixel of N40.

Fig. A.7: Same as Fig. A.2 for the central pixel of N41.

Fig. A.8: Same as Fig. A.2 for the central pixel of N36.

Fig. A.9: LTE model errors for all species (rows) in components (columns) of clump N44. The cores SMA 7 in MM1 and SMA 3 in MM2 are marked by ‘1’ and ‘2’, respectively, and the clump of N44 is marked by a star (as designated in Zapata et al. 2012 and Motte et al. 2007).

Fig. A.10: Same as Fig. A.9 for clump N38. The corresponding LTE model results are in Fig. 5

Fig. A.12: Same as Fig. A.9 for the N region, containing clumps N40, N41, and N36. The corresponding LTE model results are in Fig. 6.

Fig. A.11: Same as Fig. A.9 for clump N48. The corresponding LTE model results are in Fig. 4.

857 **Appendix B: Production and destruction routes**
858 **from the NAUTILUS model**

Fig. B.1: The production (top) and destruction (bottom) routes for H_2CO , components 1 and 2. The reactions are described in each legend. The designation gr() stands for a grain surface process.

Fig. B.2: Same as Fig. B.1 for H_2CO component 3.

Fig. B.3: Same as Fig. B.1 for CH_3CCH , both components.

Fig. B.4: Same as Fig. B.1 for CH_3OH component 2.

Fig. B.5: Same as Fig. B.1 for CH₃OH component 4.

Fig. B.6: Same as Fig. B.1 for CH₃OH component 5.